

SELF-REINFORCED POLY(LACTIC ACID) (PLA) COMPOSITES WITH ENHANCED IMPACT PERFORMANCE, TENSILE PROPERTIES AND HEAT RESISTANCE

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ABSTRACT

The inherent brittleness and poor thermal resistance of poly(lactic acid) (PLA) are two main challenges towards a wider industrial application of this bioplastic. In the present work, through the development of self-reinforced PLA (SR-PLA) or "all-PLA" composites, the high brittleness and low heat deflection temperature (HDT) of PLA have been overcome, while simultaneously improving the tensile strength and modulus of SR-PLA. The obtained composites are fully biobased, recyclable and under the right conditions compostable. For the creation of SR-PLA composites, first a tape extrusion process was optimized to ensure superior mechanical properties. The results show that SR-PLA composites exhibited enhanced moduli (2.5 times) and tensile strengths (2 times) and showed 14 times increase in impact energy compared to neat PLA. Finally, the HDT of SR-PLA was also increased by about 26 °C compared to neat PLA, which is mainly derived from the increase in modulus and crystallinity.

1 INTRODUCTION

Growing public concern and new environmental legislations have created a substantial driving force for manufactures to consider the environmental impact of their products at all stages of the life cycle. For this reason, biobased and biodegradable polymers have been the subject of many studies during the past decade. Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) is one of the most promising thermoplastic biopolymers because of its attractive mechanical properties, low emission of greenhouse gases, low amount of energy used for production, potential biodegradability and high industrial production capacity. However, due to its high brittleness and low heat deflection temperature (HDT), PLA has not yet gained full market acceptance as an engineering resin. One possible strategy to improve the mechanical and thermal properties of PLA has been through the addition of natural fibres to make so-called 'green composites' [1]. Although the use of natural fibres to reinforce PLA seems at first to be an environmentally sound approach as they are renewable, there are some issues with respect to end-of-life scenarios for these composites. In the case of mechanical recycling their relatively poor thermal stability may lead to severe additional thermal degradation of the composites during subsequent reprocessing steps [2].

A promising approach to composite recycling is the concept of "self-reinforced polymer" composites (SRPs) or "all-polymer" composites, in which a polymer matrix is reinforced with oriented fibres or tapes of the same polymer. The absence of 'foreign' reinforcements means enhanced fibre-matrix interfacial adhesion and more importantly, full recyclability without the need for separation of fibre and matrix. The concept was first presented by Capiati and Porter using oriented polyethylene (PE) reinforcement and PE matrix with different melting temperatures [3]. In following several decades, it has been successfully transferred to a range of polymers using various consolidation technologies [4, 5]. In the early 2000s, Peijs and coworkers developed a co-extrusion technique based on polypropylene (PP) through which the processing temperature window could be widened to as much as 30 °C [4]. The volume fraction of reinforcement in these composites based on co-extruded tapes was extremely high (~ 90%), while various parameters could be used to adjust mechanical and interfacial properties [6]. Because of the large processing window, a wide range of composite

fabrication techniques were demonstrated by Cabrera *et al.*, including filament winding [7], non-isothermal stamping [8] and the creation of sandwich panels [9]. These SR-PP or all-PP composites are currently marketed under the trade name of PURE[®].

Figure 1: Life cycle of all-PLA composites

In present work, another family of SRPs is being presented based on the biopolymer PLA. The main advantages of using biopolymer are to create performance products from sustainable resources, competing with fossil hydrocarbon sourced polymers, at the same time leaving open the possibility of composting as an alternative end-of-life option in addition to recycling. A flow diagram summarizing the life cycle of SR-PLA composites is shown in Figure 1. PLA pellets can be synthesized from corn through a series of chemical routes. From these pellets, oriented PLA tapes are processed by extrusion and solid-state drawing. These tapes can be woven into fabric and subsequently consolidated into sheets. Finally, finished articles can be produced by thermoforming of these sheets. At the end of the products' life, they can be collected and mechanically recycled into other PLA based products such as packaging or even new SR-PLA composites. At the end of their life-time these PLA materials can finally be composted in a commercial composting facility.

To date, SR-PLA composites have been studied mainly for clinical use such as sutures, rods screws and plates. Improved strength and rigidity have been reported. Törmälä [10] manufactured SR-PLA by sintering of PLA fibres and studied the biodegradation of these composites *in vivo*. The initial flexural strength and shear strength of SR-PLA are 2.1 times and 1.4 times higher than the corresponding values of injection moulded PLA materials. Other groups also studied various physical and thermal treatments and their effects on widening the processing window [11]. Jia *et al.* [12] reported SR-PLA composites and PLA reinforced polybutylene succinate (PBS) (PLA-PBS) composites based on commercial textile grade Ingeo[™] PLA yarns from NatureWorks[®]. Despite the fact that these Ingeo[™] have rather limited mechanical performance, improved tensile strength and modulus were observed for both types of SRPs, with the highest improvements reported for SR-PLA. However, until now, impact behaviour and HDT of SR-PLA composites, which both limit the majority of applications of PLA, have not been studied. In this work, the optimisation of a tape-manufacturing route for the creation of biobased fully recyclable and potentially compostable composites is presented, together with an investigation of mechanical and thermal properties of resulting SR-PLA composite laminates.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

Materials. NatureWorks[®] Ingeo[™] PLA 4032D and 3051D polymers were used for the reinforcing tapes and the matrix phase, respectively. Both grades are poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA). Unless otherwise specified, PLA in this paper always refers to PLLA. The weight average molecular weight (M_w) of PLA 4032D and 3051D are 133,500 and 72,633 g/mol respectively, as determined by means of gel permeation chromatograph (GPC) in chloroform. The melting temperatures (T_m) of the PLAs used are

approximately 169 °C for the oriented tapes and 154 °C for the matrix phase, as measured by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC).

Manufacture of PLA tapes. A Collin single screw extruder was employed to obtain a PLA extruded film. This extruded film was quenched by winding on a chill roll, followed by post-drawing on heated rollers to create an oriented tape. The tapes were drawn in a two-step solid-state drawing process below the melting temperature. The first drawing step provided some initial orientation, but ultimate drawing was performed in the second step. Multiplication of the first draw ratio (velocity ratio of the two drums of the drawing unit), and the second draw ratio, gives total draw ratio.

Manufacture of SR-PLA composites. Unidirectional (UD) and bi-directional (BD) laminates with a thickness of ~ 1.6 mm (67 vol.% of tape) were manufactured by stacking in a $[0]_{20}$ or $[0, 90]_{10}$ lay-up configuration in a mould. To avoid coupling effects, the cross-ply laminates were made symmetric, which means that each ply is mirrored (in terms of thickness and orientation) about the mid-plane. Laminates were produced at a compaction pressure of 2.5 MPa and a temperature of 150 or 160 °C. The entire cycle from insertion of the mould into the press until removal of the consolidated laminate took approximately 30 min. All test specimens were then cut from the laminates using a band saw to the required dimensions.

Characterization. DSC was conducted on Mettler-Toledo 822e. All samples were heated to 200 °C at 10 °C/min under a N₂ atmosphere. Tensile tests were performed using an Instron 5586 at room temperature, equipped with a 10 kN load cell at a crosshead speed of 10% strain/min. Impact performance of BD laminates was measured using a penetrating dart test on a Zwick Rel tensile machine. Laminates (60 × 60 mm) were clamped between two plates with an internal diameter of 20 mm. A hemispherical dart with a diameter of 10 mm was used and impact energies were obtained by recording the load-time curve during penetration. The constant speed during penetration was 1 m/s. A Q800 dynamic mechanical analyser (DMA) from TA Instruments was used for determining HDT. A constant load of 1.83 MPa was applied at the mid-point of a 3-point bending sample according to ATSM Standard D648. The sample was heated at the rate of 2 °C/min from -10 to 170 °C. The sample displacement was recorded as a function of temperature. Wide angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) 2D patterns were recorded on the BM26 beamline at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF). The energy of the X-ray beam was 1.033 Å. The sample-to-detector distance was 138.6 mm. All the images were corrected for background scattering. Morphological studies were carried out on gold-coated samples using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (FEI Inspector-F, The Netherlands).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical behavior of PLA tapes

It is expected that the mechanical properties will improve with increasing DR because of increasing strain-induced crystallization and orientation. Figure 2(a) shows typical stress-strain curves of the PLA reinforcement tape prepared at 90 °C upon different draw ratios. For drawn PLA tapes, the strain hardening is observed after yielding. The slope of the strain hardening is strongly related to the DR. Upon drawing only 4 times of PLA film, the slope of strain hardening actually already jumps. The higher the DR, the greater is the strain hardening. This can be explained as the strain-induced crystallinity and orientation. The strain-hardening behavior is advantageous to industrial thermoforming processes because it assists in the production of higher quality films with uniform thickness, named self-level [13]. As expected, drawing has a positive effect on modulus and strength of tapes. Compared to extruded PLA film (1.8 GPa in modulus and 53 MPa in tensile strength), a 128% and 227% increase in Young's modulus and tensile strength have been achieved for the oriented tapes of DR=8 drawn at 90 °C (4.1 GPa in modulus and 174 MPa in tensile strength), respectively (see Table 1).

It was reported that for a fixed draw ratio, the 2nd drawing temperature can have a dramatic effect on mechanical properties [14]. For this set of experiments, tapes were produced at a constant take-up speed and increasing drawing temperature (T_d) in the second step from 70 to 130 °C in 20 °C increments. A significant influence of T_d on the overall mechanical behaviour can be seen. Young's modulus and tensile strength of the post drawn tapes increases with T_d , with maximum values obtained for tapes drawn at 130 °C. The Young's modulus and tensile strength for tapes drawn at 130 °C are 6.7

GPa and 278 MPa, respectively. These values are 4.7 times and 1.5 times higher than for tapes drawn at 70 °C. Compared to isotropic PLA films, a 3.7 and 5.2 times increase in Young's modulus and tensile strength is achieved.

Figure 2: Stress-strain curves of PLA films and tapes subjected to (a) various draw ratios ($T_d=90$ °C), and (b) different drawing temperatures (DR=8).

Table 1: Tensile properties, Herman's orientation factors and crystallinity (X_c) of various PLLA tapes

T_d [°C]	DR	Herman's factor (200/110)	X_c [%]	Young's modulus [GPa]	Tensile strength [MPa]	Energy to break* [J/m ³]
Extruded	1	-	4	1.8±0.1	53±2	5.9×10 ⁶
90	4	0.99	53	3.5±0.1	157±7	-
90	5	0.98	53	4.0±0.2	172±12	-
90	8	-	55	4.1±0.4	174±13	3.8×10 ⁷
110	8	0.99	61	5.8±0.2	248±26	6.3×10 ⁷
130	8	0.99	67	6.7±0.4	278±7	7.5×10 ⁷

* Energy to break = $\int_0^{\varepsilon_f} \sigma d\varepsilon$, where σ is stress, ε is strain, and ε_f is the failure strain.

Interestingly, in comparison to the brittle tensile behaviour of un-oriented PLA, a much more ductile behaviour is observed after drawing. Compared to isotropic PLA, a 3.2 and 12.7 times increase in elongation at break and energy to break is obtained for tapes drawn at 130 °C. In contrast to the relatively smooth fracture surface of isotropic PLA, fibrillation takes place during the fracture process of these drawn tapes. In these oriented specimens, growing cracks are arrested by the anisotropic microstructure and catastrophic failure is postponed [15]. As a result, not only modulus and tensile strength but also ductility is greatly enhanced for tapes drawn at 130 °C.

The maximum tensile modulus and strength that could be achieved in this work were 6.7 GPa and 0.28 GPa, respectively. These tensile properties are comparable to the maximum moduli of 6-9.2 GPa and strength of 0.28-0.87 GPa, previously reported for drawing of melt-crystallized films of PLA in the solid-state below T_m (170-180 °C). The relatively low tensile strength properties obtained in the present work accounts for cumulative effects of lower molecular weight, orientation of molecular chains and crystallinity that develops during drawing. Moreover, here we produced tapes rather than fibres, which are known to possess lower tensile strengths than fibres. In general, the properties of PLA fibres or tapes are rather low when compared to those of oriented PE, PP or PET fibres or tapes [4]. The reason for this is the low intrinsic modulus of a PLA crystal. Nishino *et al.* reported the crystal modulus of an α -form crystal of PLLA by using X-ray diffraction [16]. They reported 12 GPa for the crystal modulus of α -form along the chain axis, meaning that the theoretically maximum

achievable Young's modulus of a PLA fibre is well below the experimentally reported moduli for PE, PP and PET, which all have much higher crystal moduli [17].

Overall, it can be concluded that drawing at 130 °C on the pilot line lead to good quality tapes as moduli of 6.7 GPa for these melt-crystallized PLA tapes compares well with a theoretical modulus of 12 GPa. Because of this, the highly oriented PLA tapes drawn at 130 °C were used as the reinforcement phase for SR-PLA composites.

Figure 3: SEM cross-section images of (a) extruded films and tapes drawn at 90 °C with DR of (b) 4, (c) 5, and (d) 8. Arrow indicates the stretching directions.

3.2 Structure variation of PLA tapes

DSC was performed to find the development in crystallinity after drawing. As seen in Table 1, the extruded films were almost amorphous (4% crystallinity content). Preparing amorphous film is very important, because a too high initial crystallinity reduced the maximum attainable draw ratio and consequently lowered the final tape mechanical properties. In agreement, Hyon and co-workers [18] started from as-spun fibres with crystallinity not higher than 5%, and drawn them six times. For tapes drawn at 90 °C, the crystallinity increased dramatically to 53% and then reached a plateau at DR=4. Furthermore, it is clear that increasing the drawing temperature results in higher degree of crystallinity. Therefore, the improved modulus and strength with T_d can be attributed to an increase in crystallinity.

2D WAXS was performed to determine the PLA orientation after stretching. Herman's orientation factor (f) calculated from Gaussian function is used to quantify the orientation of PLA, and the corresponding values for various tapes are listed in Table 1. The PLA extruded film shows a diffuse isotropic scatter typical of an amorphous polymer. The Herman's orientation factors of PLA tapes drawn at 90 °C are 0.99 and 0.98 for DR=4 and 5, respectively, suggesting crystals with good orientation. Besides, high degrees of orientation of the crystalline phase were also observed in PLA tapes drawn at 110 °C and 130 °C.

SEM was performed to observe the morphology of the fracture surfaces. As seen in Figure 3, the alignment of lamellae stacks can be viewed clearly for tapes draw at DR=4. Denser packing of lamellae is found in tape draw at DR=5 and DR=8.

3.3 Tensile properties of SR-PLA composites

Figure 4: Comparison of mechanical property for PLA tape and UD SR-PLA composites with other composites.

Figure 4 compares the mechanical properties of PLA tape, unidirectional (UD) and bi-directional (BD) SR-PLA composites obtained in present work with commercial PLA based composites as well as oriented PP and SR-PP composites. Compared to isotropic PLA, the modulus and strength of UD SR-PLA laminate consolidated at 160 °C increases to 4.4 GPa and 102 MPa, which is an improvement of about 144% and 92%, respectively. Still these values are lower than those of PLA tapes. SR-PLA composites consisting of amorphous sheets as matrix and commercial grade Ingeo™ PLA yarns and fabrics from NatureWorks® were prepared by Li *et al.* [11]. For UD SR-PLA composites with 25 wt.% yarns, a Young's modulus of 3.7 GPa and tensile strength of 58.6 MPa were reported. In our work, the Young's modulus (6.7 GPa) and tensile strength (278 MPa) of the reinforcement tapes are considerably higher than the those of the PLA yarns (1.1 GPa and 133 MPa) used in their work. Moreover, higher reinforcement content was achieved due to the tape geometry that allows for a 'brick-and-mortar' composite morphology, leading to higher tensile properties. Particularly the tensile strength of the current SR-PLA composites compares very favourably with other SR-PLA composites, with tensile strength nearly twice than that of SR-PLA based on Ingeo™ yarns [4].

Two compaction temperatures were used to prepare BD SR-PLA laminates, but with only little effect on tensile modulus and strength. The slightly increase in tensile properties at high compaction temperatures is due to the increased interfacial bonding and better load transfer.

Compared to glass fibre or natural fibre reinforced PLA composites, although the modulus of UD SR-PLA sheet is lower, the tensile strength is outstanding and exceeds that of the rest PLA-based composites shown in the figure. Therefore, SR-PLA composites could be of particular interest for products where strength is critical.

3.4 Impact properties of SR-PLA composites

Figure 5 shows the penetration impact energy absorbed by different composite laminates, normalized for specimen thickness. Clearly, isotropic PLA shows very low energy absorption. On the other hand, SR-PLA composites absorbed significantly more energy compared to isotropic PLA. As described earlier, the energy required to break a tape is 12.7 times higher than that of isotropic PLA film. Therefore, the tensile failure of PLA tapes in SR-PLA composites is expected to attribute greatly to the total energy absorption. Moreover, during impact, delamination, fibrillation and tape pull-out are additional processes that can potentially absorb significant amounts of energy.

The energy increases from 0.5 J/mm for isotropic PLA to 6.8 J/mm for SR-PLA compacted at 150 °C, which is nearly a 14 times increase. Although the value of SR-PLA is lower than that of reported for SR-PP laminates, it is still a remarkable improvement. Furthermore, with increasing compaction temperature of SR-PLA, absorbed impact energy is reduced. Similar effects were reported for SR-PP composites [19, 20] and are related to the fact that weak interfaces can have positive effects on energy absorption by allowing more delamination and less localization of the impact damage, with a greater volume of composite being involved in energy absorption process.

The inset of Figure 5 shows typical impact penetration damage. Isotropic PLA shows lower, more localized, energy absorption since the deformation is limited to the immediate impact site, unlike SR-PLA specimen which shows large deformations, large amounts of fibrillation and delamination, and thus high energy absorption.

Figure 5: Impact energy normalised for specimen thickness. (Insert) image of typical impact penetration damage.

3.5 Heat deflection temperature (HDT) of SR-PLA composites

As seen in Table 2, the HDT of SR-PLA composites increased compared to that of isotropic PLA. UD SR-PLA compacted at 160 °C exhibits the highest HDT (~ 83 °C). This value suggests that the upper service temperature limit for PLA increases with drawing. The improved heat resistance in SR-PLA laminates is mainly derived from the increase in modulus as well as crystallinity. This improvement in HDT for SR-PLA by 26 °C is useful for many applications and similar to annealed PLA [21], while being slightly below that of stereocomplex PLA [22]. Compared to other plastics, UD SR-PLA composites exhibit a similar HDT as polystyrene (PS) (~ 85 °C), which is often used in food packaging, and acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) (~ 88 °C). UD SR-PLA composites have a higher HDT than nylon 6 (~ 60 °C), PP (~ 70 °C), and PET (~ 65 °C) [23]. This could open up new markets for PLA bioplastics such as consumer electronics, packaging, vehicle-interior components, and a great deal more.

Table 2: The heat deflection temperature (HDT) and corresponding crystallinity (X_c) of the PLA and SR-PLA composites.

Sample	PLA	BD SR-PLA at 150 °C	BD SR-PLA at 160 °C	UD SR-PLA at 160 °C
HDT [°C]	57±1	67±2	66±2	83±3
X_c [%]	8.1	52.3	48.6	48.7

4 CONCLUSIONS

Both draw ratio and drawing temperature play an important role in the morphology and resulting properties. An increase in modulus and strength is seen with increasing draw ratio, due to the strain-induced crystallization and orientation. Drawing at higher temperature increases the modulus and strength further, which accounts for the improved crystallinity. Ultimately, high-modulus (6.7 GPa), high-strength (280 MPa) PLA tapes with DR=8 drawn at 130 °C were chosen as the reinforcements for SR-PLA composites. The obtained SR-PLA composites exhibited enhanced moduli (2.5 times) and tensile strengths (2 times) and showed 14 times increase in impact energy compared to neat PLA. Finally, the HDT of SR-PLA was also increased by about 26 °C compared to neat PLA. The multiple end-of-life options offered by SR-PLA composites, including recycling and compositing, empowers them to reduce the environmental impact of materials, and gives the end-user maximum flexibility in selecting environmentally sound waste disposal schemes.

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REFERENCES

- [1] L.A. Berglund and T. Peijs, Cellulose biocomposites-from bulk moldings to nanostructured systems, *MRS Bulletin*, **35**, 2010, pp. 201-207.
- [2] N. Cabrera, B. Alcock, J. Loos and T. Peijs, Processing of all-polypropylene composites for ultimate recyclability, *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part L: Journal of Materials Design and Applications*, **218**, 2004, pp.145-155.
- [3] N.J. Capiati and R.S. Porter, The concept of one polymer composites modelled with high density polyethylene, *Journal of Materials Science*, **10**, 1975, pp. 1671-1677.
- [4] B. Alcock and T. Peijs, *Technology and development of self-reinforced polymer composites*, Polymer Composites-Polyolefin Fractionation-Polymeric Peptidomimetics-Collagens: Springer; 2013. p. 1-76.
- [5] I. Ward and P. Hine, The science and technology of hot compaction, *Polymer*, **45**, 2004, pp. 1413-1427.
- [6] B. Alcock, N. Cabrera, N.M. Barkoula, J. Loos and T. Peijs, Interfacial properties of highly oriented coextruded polypropylene tapes for the creation of recyclable all - polypropylene composites, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **104**, 2007, pp. 118-129.
- [7] N. Cabrera, B. Alcock, E. Klompen and T. Peijs, Filament winding of co-extruded polypropylene tapes for fully recyclable all-polypropylene composite products, *Applied Composite Materials*, **15**, 2008, pp. 27-45.
- [8] N. Cabrera, C. Reynolds, B. Alcock and T. Peijs, Non-isothermal stamp forming of continuous tape reinforced all-polypropylene composite sheet, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **39**, 2008, pp.1455-1466.
- [9] N. Cabrera, B. Alcock and T. Peijs, Design and manufacture of all-PP sandwich panels based on co-extruded polypropylene tapes, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **39**, 2008, pp. 1183-1195.
- [10] P. Törmälä. Bioabsorbable surgical composite materials, *Advanced Materials*, **4**, 1992, pp. 589-591.
- [11] R. Li and D. Yao, Preparation of single poly (lactic acid) composites, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **107**, 2008, pp. 2909-2916.
- [12] W. Jia, R.H. Gong and P.J. Hogg, Poly (lactic acid) fibre reinforced biodegradable composites, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **62**, 2014, pp. 104-112.

- [13] M.O. Oh and S.H. Kim, Conformational development of polylactide films induced by uniaxial drawing, *Polymer International*, **63**, 2014, pp. 1247-1253.
- [14] T. Schimanski, T. Peijs, P.J. Lemstra and J. Loos, Influence of postdrawing temperature on mechanical properties of melt-spun isotactic polypropylene, *Macromolecules*, **37**, 2004, pp. 1810-1815.
- [15] D.W. Grijpma, H. Altpeter, M.J. Bevis and J. Feijen, Improvement of the mechanical properties of poly (D,L - lactide) by orientation, *Polymer International*, **51**, 2002, PP. 845-851.
- [16] T. Nishino, M. Tanaka and K. Nakamae, Elastic moduli of the crystalline regions of biodegradable polymers, *Polymer Preprints Japan-English Edition*, **49**, 2000, pp. 316.
- [17] B. Crist, The ultimate strength and stiffness of polymers, *Annual Review of Materials Science*, **25**, 1995, pp.295-323.
- [18] S.H. Hyon, K. Jamshidi and Y. Ikada, *Melt spinning of poly-L-lactide and hydrolysis of the fiber in vitro*, Polymers As Biomaterials: Springer; 1984. pp. 51-65.
- [19] B. Alcock, N. Cabrera, N.M. Barkoula and T. Peijs, Low velocity impact performance of recyclable all-polypropylene composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **66**, 2006, pp. 1724-1737.
- [20] B. Alcock, N. Cabrera, N.M. Barkoula, Z. Wang and T. Peijs. The effect of temperature and strain rate on the impact performance of recyclable all-polypropylene composites, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **39**, 2008, pp. 537-547.
- [21] Z. Tang, C. Zhang, X. Liu and J. Zhu, The crystallization behavior and mechanical properties of polylactic acid in the presence of a crystal nucleating agent, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, **125**, 2012, pp. 1108-1115.
- [22] B.U. Nam and B.S. Lee, Toughening of PLA stereocomplex by Impact modifiers, *Journal of the Korea Academia-Industrial cooperation Society*, **13**, 2012, pp. 919-925.
- [23] Heat Deflection Temperature Testing of Plastics 2014 [October 29, 2014]. Available from: <http://www.matweb.com/reference/deflection-temperature.aspx>.